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**USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR POSE
ESTIMATION AND GESTURE RECOGNITION**

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ABSTRACT

The work comprises 38 pages, 21 figures and 53 references.

Keywords: Real-time object detection, object tracking, convolutional neural networks, top-down pose estimation, real-time multi-object pose estimation.

The central theme of this research is the application of advanced artificial intelligence technologies for analyzing human hand movements using data obtained from optical sensors such as cameras. The main goal is the development of effective algorithms and machine learning models capable of identifying, tracking, and analyzing the hand's skeletal structure, with subsequent gesture recognition for intuitive remote control of electronic devices.

The aim of this work is a deep exploration and systematic comparison of existing methodologies and technological approaches to solving the complex task of gesture recognition. This includes analysis of individual modules that play a critical role in the gesture recognition process, in particular the pose estimation modules which allow precise interpretation of user movements, and specialized recognition algorithms that can accurately identify specific gestures based on the collected data.

For software development in this work, the following technologies were chosen: the Python programming language [1], the TensorFlow machine learning library [2], and the PyTorch machine learning library [3].

The final product of the research is high-efficiency software code that provides reliable real-time detection and pose estimation of human hands, and also enables gesture recognition for controlling various devices. Thus, this work aims not only to contribute to the development of the theoretical foundations of gesture recognition, but also to foster new practical solutions for improving the interactivity of user devices through the effective implementation of advanced gesture recognition technologies.

The application of this technology is not limited to a single domain and has the potential to revolutionize human-machine interaction in many fields, including automated control of home appliances, sign language translation, augmented reality

development, and much more, opening new possibilities for more intuitive communication between people and technology.

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INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the Gesture Recognition Problem. The importance of the gesture recognition problem has grown significantly in recent decades, especially with the development of machine learning, computer vision, and smart devices. This technology plays an important role in the field of human–computer interaction, providing new ways to work with digital devices and systems without physical contact. Gesture recognition is also key to creating intuitive interfaces in virtual and augmented reality, allowing users to effectively control virtual environments. Additionally, this technology improves interaction with smart devices and is used in security systems as an alternative to traditional authentication methods.

Current State of Research in Gesture Recognition. With the advent of neural networks, all modern research in the field of computer vision has changed dramatically. As of today, convolutional neural networks have become the cornerstone of gesture recognition research, opening up a new, previously unseen space for exploration. Moreover, current works in this field have reframed the problem, finding a close connection with object recognition and pose estimation. These methods achieve the required accuracy and also enable real-time gesture recognition on consumer devices.

Aim and Objectives of the Work. The aim of this work is to investigate and compare modern methods for solving the gesture recognition task, and to implement the most suitable approach in a working system. To accomplish this aim, the following objectives were set:

1. Investigate and compare contemporary methods of solving the gesture recognition problem.
2. Select and implement the most applicable approach to solving the problem.
3. Perform testing of the implemented system, obtaining the relevant accuracy and speed metrics.

1. THEORY

1.1 Neural Networks

Gesture recognition using a camera is a complex task that involves identifying and interpreting hand and finger movements in real time. Neural networks are ideal for pattern recognition because they can effectively analyze visual data, extracting important features from large amounts of data without the need to explicitly define those features beforehand. Thanks to their ability to learn from examples, neural networks can adapt to various lighting conditions, hand positions, and individual user gesture characteristics. This allows the creation of flexible and reliable gesture recognition systems capable of operating in real time with high accuracy.

A neural network is a mathematical model that imitates the operation of a biological brain to solve certain tasks by transforming input data into output data in a specific way. At the core of a neural network is a set of interconnected neurons that can receive, process, and transmit signals. Below we define the basic concepts that will be used throughout this research.

A neuron is the basic computational element of a neural network, modeled as a weighted sum of its inputs plus a bias, passed through a nonlinear activation function. The formula for a single neuron can be represented as:

$$f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right), \text{ where}$$

x_i are input signals, w_i are synaptic weights, b is bias, f is an activation function.

An activation function is a function that determines the neuron's output based on the sum of input signals. Examples include the sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent, and ReLU [13] among others.

An architecture is a specific arrangement of neurons and their layers. Neural networks can have different architectures depending on the task. The simplest

architecture is a single-layer perceptron, where all inputs are connected to each output. More complex networks, such as multilayer perceptrons (MLP) [14], convolutional neural networks (CNN) [15] and recurrent neural networks (RNN) [16], contain multiple layers of neurons, each of which performs its own computations.

Training a neural network is the process of adapting the weights of a neural network to minimize the difference between actual and predicted data. In most cases, optimizing a machine learning model's parameters is done via the backpropagation algorithm [12], which uses gradient descent to adjust the weights.

A loss function is a differentiable metric that measures how well the neural network is performing, i.e. how closely the network's predictions match the actual data. It is used to guide improvements to the model. Examples include mean squared error, cross-entropy, etc.

In the context of neural networks, the gesture recognition task can be formulated as a classification problem, i.e. an optimization task where the goal is to minimize the discrepancy between predicted and actual class labels. We can view a neural network as a composition of functions that takes an input vector x and transforms it into an output y representing the predicted category. In general, this can be expressed as:

$$y = f(x; \theta), \text{ where}$$

x is an input data tensor, y is the output representing the class to which the input data belongs, θ are the model's parameters (weights) to be optimized.

1.2 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a class of deep learning neural networks optimized for analyzing visual images. The main factor distinguishing CNNs from other architectures is their ability to automatically and adaptively learn spatial hierarchies of features from images, thanks to the convolution operation which allows them to detect complex visual features at different levels of abstraction (including very high-level features). The primary components of most CNNs are convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers.

The convolutional layer performs the convolution operation (or more precisely, cross-correlation), which involves applying a filter (kernel) to the input image or the output of the previous layer to detect certain features. Formally, for two-dimensional data (for example, an image), cross-correlation is defined as:

$$(f * g)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n f(m, n) \cdot g(i - m, j - n), \text{ where}$$

f is a filter of size $F \times F$, g is an input image or previous layer output, (a tensor of size $W \times H$)

A pooling layer is a layer that reduces the dimensionality of the input data while preserving important features. Common examples are max pooling and average pooling.

A fully connected layer is a layer where all inputs from the previous layer are connected to each neuron. It is often used at the end of neural networks to classify the input data based on the features extracted.

Training CNNs is done through backpropagation of error and weight optimization using algorithms such as gradient descent. During training, the weights of the filters in convolutional layers, as well as the weights in fully connected layers, are optimized to minimize the loss function.

CNNs have proven to be extremely effective for a variety of image processing tasks, including image classification, object detection, various forms of segmentation,

and many others. They are able to detect features at different levels of abstraction, which makes them a powerful tool in deep learning.

1.3 Transformer Neural Networks

Transformer architectures [45], originally introduced in modern natural language processing (NLP), have achieved great success in various computer vision tasks, including pose estimation.

In the classic variant presented in the paper *Attention Is All You Need* [45], the attention mechanism works as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right) V,$$

where Q, K, V are the query, key, and value matrices respectively, d_k is the dimensionality of the key vectors, and the softmax function is defined as:

$$\text{softmax}(z)_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{z_j}},$$

This mechanism uses three weight matrices: W_Q, W_K, W_V , which are model parameters. These matrices serve to project the input data into query (Q), key (K), and value (V) components respectively — these components are linear projections of the input data tensor. Then a softmax is applied to the normalized product of the Q and K matrices and multiplied by the values V.

Figure 1 – Schematic of the attention mechanism from "Attention is All You Need" [45].

Figure 2 – Visualization of the attention mechanism [46].

This idea was later reinvented in the context of image processing, giving rise to the concept of Vision Transformers [47]. In this approach, the image is divided into patches of fixed size, linear embeddings are applied to each patch, positional embeddings are added, and the resulting sequence of vectors is fed into a transformer encoder. To perform classification, we use the standard approach – a special “classification token” is appended to the sequence, which the model can use for learning.

Figure 3 – Visualization of the principle of a classic Vision Transformer [47].

1.4 Object Detection

Object detection is a task in computer vision that involves identifying instances of real-world objects. The goal is to determine whether instances of specific object categories are present in an image and, if so, to localize each instance by outputting a bounding box around it. In general, there are two main paradigms for object detection: anchor-based object detection and anchor-free object detection (first proposed in FCOS [17]).

The anchor-based object detection task can be formulated as follows:

$$f: X \rightarrow Y, \text{ where}$$

$$X: \{x \in X \mid x = I\}, Y = \{(\Delta b_{a_1}, c_1, P_1), (\Delta b_{a_2}, c_2, P_2), \dots, (\Delta b_{a_n}, c_n, P_n)\},$$

I is a tensor of dimensions (h, w, c) , where h is the input image height, w is the width, c is the number of channels., $\Delta b_{ai} = (\Delta x_{ai}, \Delta y_{ai}, \Delta w_{ai}, \Delta h_{ai})$ and $\Delta x_{ai}, \Delta y_{ai}$ are the center offsets, $\Delta w_{ai}, \Delta h_{ai}$ are the scale change for the anchor box of the i -th object, c_i is the class of the i -th object, p_i is the confidence score for the i -th object, $p_i \in [0; 1]$.

The adjustments Δb_{ai} are applied to a predefined anchor box to obtain the desired bounding box that precisely matches the actual object in the image.

Formally, the anchor-free object detection task can be formulated as:

$$f: X \rightarrow Y, \text{ where}$$

$$X: \{x \in X \mid x = I\}, Y = \{(B_1, c_1, P_1), (B_2, c_2, P_2), \dots, (B_n, c_n, P_n)\},$$

I is a tensor of dimensions (h, w, c) , where h is the input image height, w is the width, c is the number of channels, $B_i = (x_{min}, y_{min}, x_{max}, y_{max})$ or $(x_{center}, y_{center}, width, height)$ are the coordinates of the bounding box for i -th object, c_i is the class of the i -th object, p_i is the confidence for the i -th object, $p_i \in [0; 1]$.

Initially, most object detection systems built the model's output using anchors [\[20\]](#). However, the most effective modern object detection solutions [\[18\]](#), [\[19\]](#) now predominantly use anchor-free methods.

1.5 Pose Estimation

Pose estimation is the task of estimating the pose of one or more objects within an image or sequence of images. In the context of human pose estimation, this involves finding the spatial locations of key points of the body. Formally, given an image I , the goal of pose estimation is to determine the positions of N key points that define a pose:

$$f: X \rightarrow Y,$$

$$X: \{x \in X \mid x = I\},$$

$$Y: \{y \in Y \mid y = [P_1, P_2, \dots, P_S]\},$$

$$P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_j], p = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \text{ where}$$

I is a tensor of dimensions (h, w, c) , where h is the image height, w is the width, c is the number of channels,

j - the number of joints, (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are the coordinates of each joint in the image space R^n .

In general, there are two approaches to solving the pose estimation problem: the top-down approach and the bottom-up approach.

Top-Down Pose Estimation

In the top-down approach, each object (person) is first detected separately, and then pose estimation is performed for each detected instance. This process can be divided into two main stages:

- a) **Object detection:** identifying and localizing objects (people) in the image.
- b) **Pose estimation:** for each detected object, the model predicts the positions of the key points within that object's bounding box.

Formally, this approach involves the sequential application of an object detection function D that identifies objects, and a pose estimation function F :

$$B = D(X; \theta_D),$$

$$Y = F(\text{Crop}(X, B); \theta_F), \text{ where}$$

B are the bounding boxes of objects obtained from the object detection model's output,

$\text{Crop}(X, B)$ is an operation that extracts from image I the region specified by a bounding box B , θ_D and θ_F are the parameters of the detection and pose estimation models, respectively.

Bottom-Up Pose Estimation

On the other hand, the bottom-up approach begins with detecting all relevant key points in the image, regardless of which instance they belong to, and then grouping these key points into separate instances during a post-processing stage. Specifically:

a) **Detect all key points in the image.** This step outputs a set of key points without associating them with specific objects or people.

b) **Group the detected key points** into separate instances based on spatial (and possibly temporal) proximity or learned feature affinities.

Formally, this approach involves the sequential application of a keypoint detection function G that identifies key points, and a keypoint grouping function H :

$$K = G(X; \theta_G),$$

where K are the detected key points and θ_G are the parameters of the keypoint detection model.

Then the grouping function H organizes these points into separate sets representing individual poses:

$$Y = H(K; \theta_H), \text{ where}$$

θ_H are the parameters of the grouping model, which may include learned affinities or geometric constraints between key points.

Both approaches have their advantages and disadvantages. For example, the bottom-up approach can be more efficient in scenarios with a large number of objects or people, since it does not require a separate pose estimation step for each instance. However, it generally has lower accuracy than the top-down approach.

In practice, most pose estimation approaches consider the subsequent localization of key points either as regression of their coordinates (for example, [[34](#), [35](#), [36](#)]) or as heatmap regression (for example, [[37](#), [38](#), [39](#), [40](#)]).

1.6 Gesture Recognition

Gesture recognition using data from optical sensors is formulated as follows: Let N be the number of possible gesture classes. Then, given a set of S input images (each being a tensor I of dimensions (h, w, c) , where h is image height, w is width, c is the number of channels), we need to construct a model

$$f: X \rightarrow Y, \text{ where } X: \{x \in X \mid x = [I_1, I_2, \dots, I_S]\}, Y = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$$

which uses an internal representation of images to assign each image to one of N classes. This formulation is characteristic of early scientific works in the field [4], [5]. Some modern studies use a similar formulation of input data, but do not treat it strictly as a classification task [6] (they might incorporate sequential models or regression-based evaluation).

Most modern scientific works [7], [8], [9], [10] formulate the domain of the gesture recognition function f (mapping inputs to gesture classes) as:

$$f: X \rightarrow Y,$$

$$X: \{x \in X \mid x = [P_1, P_2, \dots, P_S]\},$$

$$P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_j], p = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \text{ where}$$

j is the number of joints, (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are coordinates of each joint in R^n .

Accordingly, these $P_i, i = \overline{1, S}$ values can be obtained using a pose estimation model, as described in Section 1.5. The advantages of such an approach include simplifying the gesture recognition model and reducing the model's runtime. However, this formulation also has its drawbacks, so some research also focuses on more invariant and robust skeleton representations — for example, the DD-Net approach [11].

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE CHOSEN SOLUTION

2.1 Gesture Recognition

Due to the constraints that a machine learning model for real-time gesture recognition must satisfy, **DD-Net (Double-feature Double-motion Network)** [11] was chosen. This model has an ultra-lightweight architecture that allows it to be used on a wide range of devices, and it is the undisputed leader in accuracy compared to other solutions on datasets such as DHG-14 [22], DHG-28 [22], JHMDB [23] according to [21].

In particular, the authors of DD-Net addressed the following challenges in pose-based gesture recognition: viewpoint variation, movement speed variation, local and global motion trajectories, and uncorrelated joint indices. To handle these factors, the authors of DD-Net took a different approach from previous solutions: they simplified the input data and the network structure. The proposed JCD feature contains invariant information about joint locations. Compared to other similar features, it is easy to compute and contains fewer elements.

Let K be the number of frames in a gesture sequence, and N be the number of joints (assumed constant for each frame). Then for frame k the Cartesian coordinates in R^3 for joint n can be represented as $J_i^k = (x, y, z)$, and in R^2 they can be represented as $J_i^k = (x, y)$. Thus, we have the set of joints for frame k :

$$S_k = \{J_{k_1}, J_{k_2}, \dots, J_{k_N}\}$$

and the Joint Coordinate Difference (JCD^k) feature can be defined as a matrix D whose

$$JCD^k = \begin{bmatrix} \left\| \overrightarrow{J_2^k J_1^k} \right\| & & & & \\ & \vdots & \ddots & & \\ & & \vdots & \cdots & \ddots \\ \left\| \overrightarrow{J_N^k J_1^k} \right\| & & & \cdots & \cdots & \left\| \overrightarrow{J_N^k J_{N-1}^k} \right\| \end{bmatrix}$$

elements are the pairwise distances between joints J_i^k and J_j^k ($i \neq j$).

At the input of the machine learning model, this triangular distance matrix is flattened into a vector of dimension $\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$.

Since the JCD^k feature contains no information about motion speed, we also compute temporal differences of the joint coordinates. Because gestures can contain both fast and slow movements, to form a comprehensive motion descriptor, DD-Net uses both types of motion. DD-Net captures motion at two time scales (fast and slow). In practice, this means computing joint displacements over a short interval and a long interval. Each produces a motion matrix (for fast and slow motion), which is flattened into a vector. In practice, this means computing joint displacement over a short time interval (capturing fast motions) and over a longer interval (capturing slow motions). Both resulting motion matrices are then flattened into vectors, and a linear interpolation is applied so that these motion feature vectors have the same dimension as the JCD^k feature vector.

$$M_{slow}^k = S^{k+1} - S^k, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K - 1\},$$

$$M_{fast}^k = S^{k+2} - S^k, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K - 2\}$$

Most neural networks inherently assume that input data is locally correlated. However, in our case, adjacent indices in the feature vectors may correspond to joints that are not physically adjacent or correlated, which would lead to inefficient learning. To address

this problem, DD-Net projects the JCD^k feature and the dual-scale motion features into latent vectors for each frame using embedding layers.

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{JCD}^k &= \text{Embedding}_1(JCD^k) \\ \varepsilon_{M_{slow}}^k &= \text{Embedding}_1(M_{slow}^k) \\ \varepsilon_{M_{fast}}^k &= \text{Embedding}_2(M_{fast}^k)\end{aligned}$$

Embeddings here consist of sequences of neural network layers that map data from one space into another (latent) space. In this case, the embedding process can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Embedding}_1 &= \text{Conv1D}(1, 2 * \text{filters}) \rightarrow \text{Conv1D}(3, \text{filters}) \rightarrow \text{Conv1D}(1, \text{filters}), \\ \text{Embedding}_2 &= \text{Conv1D}(1, 2 * \text{filters}) \rightarrow \text{Conv1D}(3, \text{filters}) \rightarrow \text{Conv1D}(1, \text{filters}) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \rightarrow \text{Max pooling}(2),\end{aligned}$$

where *filters* — number of filters defined by the DD-Net configuration.

Thus, correlations between joints are automatically captured thanks to these embedding transformations, and this process also reduces the impact of noise in the data. Next, the latent feature embeddings are concatenated to form a combined feature representation for each frame (for example, concatenating the embedded JCD and motion features).

$$\varepsilon^k = \varepsilon_{JCD}^k \oplus \varepsilon_{M_{slow}}^k \oplus \varepsilon_{M_{fast}}^k, \quad \varepsilon^k \in R^{(K/2) \cdot \text{filters}}$$

The above-mentioned *filters* parameter essentially determines the size of the neural network; the number of parameters of the DD-Net model grows linearly with this value.

Figure 4 – Diagram of the DD-Net network architecture. “ $2 \times \text{CNN}(3, 2\text{filters}), /2$ ” denotes two Conv1D layers with kernel size 3 and number of channels = $2 \times \text{filters}$, followed by MaxPooling with stride 2. Other layers are denoted in the same format.

“GAP” stands for a global average pooling layer.

“FC” denotes fully connected layers.*

The gesture classes used for training the model (i.e., the gestures recognized) were: swipe, click start, click end, pointer, no gesture, and others. A custom dataset comprising 15 people was used to train the DD-Net model.

Figure 5 – Distribution of the number of gestures in the collected dataset. The main gesture classes each have between 1,000 and 5,000 samples.

2.2 MediaPipe Pose Estimation

Since the DD-Net gesture recognition model expects input data in the form of skeleton keypoint coordinates:

$$P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_j], p = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

the next task is to obtain the appropriate skeletal information using a pose estimation model. In the scope of our task, we only need to recognize hand gestures from one person at a time, so the most logical choice in this case is a **top-down pose estimation** approach.

At the beginning of this research, the first model chosen to tackle the pose estimation task was **MediaPipe Hands** [24] from the MediaPipe framework [25].

This solution consists of two models: a single-frame hand **palm detection** model and a subsequent **pose (landmark) regression** model.

Figure 6 – Overview of the solution using MediaPipe [26].

The first model (called **BlazePalm** [27]) is a convolutional neural network that detects palms. It processes the full image and returns bounding boxes for any detected palms.

First, because palms are relatively small objects, a non-max suppression algorithm is used, and palms are detected using square bounding boxes (anchors), ignoring other aspect ratios. This allows the number of anchors to be reduced by 3–5 times. Second, the model’s architecture consists of an encoder–decoder structure to better capture image context [28], given the high scale variance present in hand images

The second model is a pose estimator (hand landmark model), which operates on the cropped image region (the palm detector’s output) and returns 3D hand keypoint coordinates (landmarks).

Figure 7 – Architecture of the pose estimation model in MediaPipe [26].

Figure 8 – Example visualization of the MediaPipe hand pose estimator’s output [26].

The authors of this model note that the model’s mean squared error is 16.1%. Considering that their solution was developed with strict constraints on technical specifications for on-device use, this is a reasonably good result.. However, during experiments training the DD-Net gesture recognition model on data obtained via MediaPipe, it became clear that this approach drastically degraded performance.

Failures in pose estimation during relatively fast movements or under poor lighting conditions (which are common in real usage) led to sparse input matrices for the gesture recognition model and insufficient information for effective learning.

2.3 MMPose Pose Estimation

Given the shortcomings of the MediaPipe-based approach, we decided to use more accurate pose estimation models at the cost of increased processing time. In this research, we chose the **RTMPose** model [30] from the MMPose framework [31]. As of the publication of RTMPose, this solution was the most efficient among publicly available models on mobile devices, while maintaining a sufficient level of accuracy (72.2% Average Precision on the COCO dataset [32]).

RTMPose is a top-down pose estimation model. Top-down algorithms are generally considered accurate but slow, due to the additional detection step that can impact performance in scenes with many objects. However, thanks to the excellent efficiency of modern real-time object detectors [29] and [33], the detection part is no longer a bottleneck for top-down pose estimation algorithms.

First, we need to solve the problem of detecting hands in the frame; for this, we used the **RTMDet** model [29]. In their paper, the authors aimed to develop an efficient real-time object detector that outperforms the YOLO series and is easily adaptable to various objects, including those with different positions and rotations. RTMDet’s macro-architecture follows a typical one-stage object detector design.

Figure 9 – Macro-architecture of RTMDet [29]. CSP blocks with large-kernel depth-wise convolutions are used to build the backbone. Multi-level features, labeled C3, C4, and C5, are then merged in the model’s CSP-PAFPN neck, which is composed of the same blocks as the backbone. Shared-convolution heads are used for detection.

Classic YOLO approaches typically use CSPDarkNet [50] as the base architecture, which contains four stages, each consisting of several basic blocks.

Therefore, the authors of RTMDet use a similar approach, but with 5×5 convolutions in depth in the basic structural block of CSPDarkNet to increase effective receptive fields. This approach allows for more comprehensive contextual modeling and significantly improves accuracy. Since the number of layers in the basic block also increases due to the additional 1×1 convolution, this hinders parallel processing. To solve this problem, we reduce the number of blocks, but each of them has a large width.

The following loss function is used, based on the dynamic soft label assignment strategy used in SimOTA [19]:

$$C = \lambda_1 C_{cls} + \lambda_2 C_{reg} + \lambda_3 C_{center},$$

where C_{cls} is a loss classification function, C_{reg} is a regression loss function, C_{center} is a loss function relative to centers.

$$C_{cls} = CE(P, Y_{soft}) \times (Y_{soft} - P)^2,$$

where P are model predictions, CE is a categorical cross entropy, Y_{soft} are class labels taking into account IoU similarly [51].

$$C_{reg} = -\log(IoU),$$

where $IoU = \frac{A \cap B}{A \cup B}$ for restrictive frames A and B .

$$C_{center} = \alpha^{|x_{pred} - x_{gt}| - \beta},$$

where x_{pred} is the predicted center, x_{gt} is the real center, α and β are hyperparameters.

This model is open source, and a pre-trained version of the RTMDet model was used as part of this solution.

RTMPose also uses the CSPNeXt model [42] as a base model, demonstrating a good balance of speed and accuracy (since it was developed as an object detection model) and is convenient for deployment. This pose estimation model finds points using an algorithm based on SimCC [41], which treats the localization of key points as a classification task. Compared to heatmap-based algorithms [37, 38, 39, 40] the SimCC-based algorithm achieves sufficient accuracy with higher computational efficiency.

It represents a new scheme that formulates key point prediction as a classification from subpixel bins for horizontal and vertical coordinates, respectively, which offers several advantages. First, SimCC does not depend on high-resolution heat maps, which allows for a very compact architecture that does not require intermediate high-resolution images [42], no expensive zoom lenses [43]. Second, SimCC aligns the final feature map for classification instead of using global aggregation layers [36], and thus avoids the loss of spatial information. Third, quantization error can be effectively reduced by classifying coordinates at the subpixel level, without the need for additional post-processing [40]. These qualities make SimCC attractive for building lightweight pose estimation models and their subsequent deployment on various backends.

Figure 10 — RTMPose architecture, which includes a convolutional layer, a fully connected layer, and a gated attention unit (GAU) to refine the representations of K keypoints. After that, pose estimation in R^2 is considered as two classification tasks for the x -axis and y -axis coordinates to predict the horizontal and vertical locations of key points [30].

RTMPose uses Gated Attention Unit [44], which is a simplified attention mechanism. Previous approaches to pose estimation using transformers either use heatmap-based representations or store both pixel tokens and keypoint tokens, resulting in high computational costs and complicating real-time operation. In contrast, RTMPose uses a self-attention mechanism with a compact SimCC-based representation to capture keypoint dependencies, which significantly reduces the computational load and allows the model to operate in real time with increased accuracy and efficiency.

Figure 11 — Diagram of the gated attention unit (GAU) operation [44].

The gated attention unit uses less memory, has higher speed, and better performance compared to the vanilla transformer. In particular, GAU improves feed-forward networks in transformer layers using gated linear units (GLU) [48], and also elegantly defines the attention mechanism:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \varphi_u(XW_u), \\
 V &= \varphi_v(XW_v), \\
 O &= (U \odot AV)W_o,
 \end{aligned}$$

where φ is a non-linear activation function, \odot is a Hadamard product, W_u , W_v and W_o are weight matrices (tensors), X is an input data tensor.

Accordingly, attention in this context is defined as:

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{n} \text{relu}^2\left(\frac{Q(x)K(z)^T}{\sqrt{s}}\right), \quad Z = \varphi_z(XW_z),$$

where $s = 128$, Q and K linear projections of the input data tensor, and $\text{relu}^2(\cdot)$ is a ReLU function squared.

In addition, RTMPose applies several optimizations. It uses a missing-frame detection algorithm from [49] to reduce latency. It also applies a standard non-max suppression algorithm and smoothing filters to improve the post-processing of results. Since

RTMPose is also open source, its pre-trained version was used.

2.4 Post Processing

In the context of the practical application of this solution for gesture recognition, machine learning models alone are not sufficient, as their results will always contain inaccuracies. Therefore, this study also empirically tested various methods for improving the performance of the combination of these models.

Linear interpolation for exceptions was used to filter the results of the pose estimation model. In this case, exceptions O are considered values for frame i :

$$P_i \in O \mid \sqrt{(P_i - P_{i-1})^2} > \alpha, i \in \{1, N\},$$

where α is a threshold value for filtering.

This approach successfully solves the problem of false positives (detection model errors).

To filter the results of the pointer gesture, smoothing was used with the Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) algorithm.

$$EMA_t = \alpha x_t + (1 - \alpha) * EMA_{t-1} ,$$

x_t are the coordinates at time t , α is a smoothing factor $\in [0; 1]$

3. EVALUATION

3.1 Metrics

The DD-Net network was trained using *5-folds cross-validation*, where none of them contained data corresponding to the same person. The search for the best model was carried out using a parameter search grid (*grid search*), and after selecting the best models based on the results, all data was used for training. It was experimentally decided to train the models for 200 epochs, after which the precision metric ceased to improve significantly. AdamW was selected as the optimizer algorithm [53], which has an additional parameter used to reduce the likelihood of overfitting, unlike Adam [52].

Below are graphs for the DD-Net model using MediaPipe for pose estimation with the following parameters $batch\ size = 64$, $learning\ rate = 1 * 10^{-4}$, $weight_decay = 1 * 10^{-4}$.

Figure 12 — Confusion matrix for DD-Net + Mediapipe.

Figures 13-16 — Precision, recall, loss and ROC-curve for DD-Net + Mediapipe.

It can be seen that the model has problems recognizing the “None” gesture, i.e., there are too many false positives. This is due to the low quality of the Mediapipe pose estimation model and, accordingly, sparse input data matrices.

Below are graphs for the DD-Net model using MMPose with the following parameters $batch\ size = 128$, $learning\ rate = 1 * 10^3$, $weight_decay = 1 * 10^{-5}$.

Figure 17 — Confusion matrix for DD-Net + RTMPose.

*Figures 18-21 — Precision, recall, loss and ROC-curve
for DD-Net + RTMPose.*

Obviously, DD-Net performs better with high-quality input data, particularly in terms of false positives.

3.2 Limitations

Despite all the advantages of this solution, it also has limitations. One of the most obvious ones is that the proposed algorithm works with a limited number of gestures, and adding new ones requires retraining the network. This is difficult to avoid, but this requirement is directly related to the use of neural network models.

The biggest drawback of the approach implemented in this work is that the DD-Net model architecture is not capable of distinguishing between the directions of gesture movements. This means that in order to distinguish between the directions of gestures, post-processing using algorithmic approaches is required. This is because the input data, as received by the machine learning model, does not contain information about the angle of rotation relative to any center in space, and all coordinates are relative in nature. However, it should be noted that although modifying the input data format can correct this drawback, this is a topic for a separate study.

Note that the RTMPose model (in its default form) does not determine the hand's laterality (left vs. right hand). If needed, one would have to modify the authors' model [29] to add left/right hand classification.

It's also valid to criticize the system's robustness: the solution is not yet adapted to non-standard conditions such as low lighting or a user being far from the camera. This is because an error in one of the models in the solution (e.g., during detection or pose estimation) affects gesture recognition. This problem is common to many solutions that divide the overall task into subtasks, where the latter are performed by separate machine learning models.

CONCLUSIONS

This course paper provides an in-depth study of modern methods of object detection, pose estimation, and real-time gesture recognition systems. A thorough analysis of the advantages and limitations of leading approaches to pose estimation was conducted, and in the context of this analysis, a comparison of the results obtained using the Mediapipe and MMPose models was carried out, with a particular focus on their impact on the accuracy and efficiency of subsequent gesture recognition.

In this paper, a tool based on the DD-Net model was developed and implemented to train the gesture recognition system. This technology opens up significant prospects for application in a wide range of areas, from the automation of household processes to the development of interactive solutions in augmented reality and sign language translation. Its implementation has the potential to radically change the way people interact with machines, making them more intuitive and convenient.

In general, this study aims not only to expand the theoretical base in the field of gesture recognition, but also to stimulate the development of the latest practical solutions. This, in turn, contributes to increasing the level of interactivity and efficiency of user devices through innovative gesture recognition methods, opening new horizons for continuous interaction between humans and technology.

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